

INVESTIGATION OF MARITAL COMPATIBILITY OF COUPLES IN KYRGYZSTAN ACCORDING TO THEIR DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS**Zhakutbekova Sezim**

Master of Kyrgyzstan-Turkey Manas University, Institute of Social Sciences, Psychological Counseling And Guidance Program, Kyrgyzstan, Bishkek
ORCID: 009-0004-9746-0106

Efiliti Erkan

Assoc. Prof. Dr.
Kyrgyzstan-Turkey Manas University, Department Of Educational Sciences, Psychological Counseling And Guidance Program, Kyrgyzstan, Bishkek
ORCID: 0000-0003-1158-5764

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to investigate the marital compatibility of married individuals in Kyrgyzstan according to their demographic characteristics. The study examines whether there are significant differences in marital compatibility levels according to the number of children, economic status, duration of marriage, type of marriage, and employment status of married individuals. In order to achieve the defined research objective, a descriptive survey model was used as a quantitative research method. The study group consisted of 173 married individuals selected based on volunteerism in Kyrgyzstan, with 38 men and 135 women participating. The "Personal Information Form" created by the researcher to collect socio-demographic information and the "Updated Marital Compatibility Scale" were used as data collection tools. The data obtained from the participants were analyzed using the SPSS 24.0 program. To assess the differentiation of variables, the relationship of dependent variables with two categorical variables was analyzed using independent samples t-test. For analyses with multiple categorical variables, ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was used.

Keywords: Marriage, Married Individuals, Compatibility, Marital Compatibility, Demographic Characteristics.

Introduction

Throughout history, humans have felt the need to be part of a community. For this reason, the concepts of marriage and family are of vital importance for the survival of individuals and the continuity of social life. The existence of the family is crucial for individuals to fulfill their social needs, such as sharing, loving and being loved, reproduction, and communication [1].

The family, which is a small unit of society, is supported by the institution of marriage. The fact that spouses are raised in different environments and have different personality structures makes it difficult to achieve continuous fulfillment and satisfaction in the marital relationship. It is at this point that the concept of marital compatibility emerges [2].

A harmonious marriage is one in which individuals who share common views on issues related to marriage and family and are able to solve problems in an appropriate manner form the marriage. In marital compatibility, the state of the marital relationship is evaluated rather than individual feelings [3]. One of the important points emphasized in marital compatibility is that individuals should be able to make each other happy. In a study supporting this idea, it was found that continuing an unhappy marriage is negatively related to overall well-being, life satisfaction, self-esteem, and general health [4]. Therefore, the concept of marital compatibility also includes the concept of marital happiness. Concepts such as love, respect, trust, and commitment positively influence the marital relationship, while effective communication, awareness, the expression and understanding of emotions bring happiness to the marriage [5].

In marriage, compatibility problems between men and women may arise for various reasons, including personal, cultural and demographic factors. For this reason, compatibility and conflict within the family are important for the continuation of married life and personal evaluations regarding the family institution [6]. In recent years, an increase in divorces has been observed in Kyrgyzstan. According to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 45.5 thousand couples applied for marriage registration in 2023, while 12,550 divorces occurred. When compared to statistics from 2011, it was found that the number of marriages decreased by 11,000, while the number of divorces increased by 3,900. This situation further emphasizes the importance of research on the sustainability of marriages and marital compatibility. Based on these data, this study aims to answer the following question: To what extent do the demographic characteristics of married individuals in Kyrgyzstan affect marital compatibility?

Purpose of the Study:

The aim of this research is to examine the marital compatibility of couples in Kyrgyzstan according to some demographic characteristics. Sub-objectives related to these are shown below.

1. Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ significantly according to the number of children?
2. Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ significantly according to their economic status?
3. Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ significantly according to the duration of marriage?

4. Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ significantly according to the type of marriage?

5. Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ significantly according to the working status of married individuals?

Method

In this study, a descriptive survey method was used to examine the marital compatibility levels of married individuals in Kyrgyzstan in terms of demographic variables. The population of the study consists of married individuals in Kyrgyzstan. The study group is made up of a total of 173 married individuals, including 38 men and 135 women, who were selected on a voluntary basis from those living in Kyrgyzstan. Two types of data collection tools were used in the study.

These are: 1. *Personal Data Form*: A personal information form created by the researcher to collect demographic data. 2. *Revised Couple Compatibility Scale*: The Revised Couple Compatibility Scale is the 14-item version of the Couple Compatibility Scale developed by Spanier, revised by Busby and colleagues, and adapted into Turkish by Gündoğdu. The translation of the scale into Kyrgyz was carried out by Efilti and Cumgalbekov [7]. To determine the construct validity of the scale, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted, and to assess its reliability, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficients were calculated.

Findings

The analysis results related to the first sub-goal of the study, which is the question "Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals show significant differences based on the number of children?" are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Marital Compatibility Levels by Number of Children

	Group	N	X	Ss	F	p
Marital Compatibility	no	21	3,43	,55	,437	,853
	1 child	28	3,43	,69		
	2 children	36	3,28	,71		
	3 children	45	3,34	,74		
	4 children	28	3,39	,54		
	5 children	13	3,20	,71		
	7 children	2	3,44	,12		

($p < .05$)

In Table 1, the results related to whether marital compatibility significantly differs based on the number of children show that marital compatibility does not significantly differ based on the number of children ($F = 0.437$; $p > 0.05$). In other words, there is no significant difference in the levels of marital compatibility based on the number of children. When examining the arithmetic mean values, it was found that individuals

without children and those with one child had higher levels of marital compatibility compared to the other groups.

The analysis results related to the second sub-goal of the study, which is the question "Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals show significant differences based on monthly income?" are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Marital Compatibility Levels by Monthly Income

	Group	N	X	Ss	F	p
Marital Compatibility	15 ve altı	56	3,30	,55	1,904	,112
	16-29	50	3,35	,81		
	30-45	43	3,43	,66		
	46-60	16	3,69	,57		
	60 ve üstü	8	3,62	,54		

($p < .05$)

In the table above, the results regarding whether marital compatibility differs significantly according to monthly income show that marital compatibility does not differ significantly according to the monthly income variable ($F = 1.904$; $p > 0.05$). In other words, there is no significant difference in marital compatibility levels according to monthly income. However, when the arithmetic average was examined according to the income levels of the participants, it was observed

that as income increased, marital compatibility also increased. It was determined that the group with the highest marital compatibility also had the highest income level, while the group with the lowest marital compatibility had the lowest income level.

The analysis results related to the third sub-goal of the study, which is the question "Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals show significant differences based on the duration of marriage?" are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

	Group	N	X	Ss	F	p
Marital Compatibility	1 and below	19	3,44	,58	,403	,806
	1-5	32	3,45	,52		
	6-15	50	3,39	,66		
	16-25	39	3,28	,76		
	26 and over	33	3,31	,79		

Marital Compatibility Levels by Duration of Marriage

(p<.05)

In Table 3, the results related to whether marital compatibility significantly differs based on the duration of marriage show that marital compatibility does not significantly differ based on the duration of marriage ($F = 0.403$; $p > 0.05$). In other words, there is no significant difference in the levels of marital compatibility based on the duration of marriage. When examining the arithmetic mean values, it was found that individuals

married for 1-5 years had higher levels of marital compatibility compared to the other groups.

The analysis results related to the fourth sub-goal of the study, which is the question "Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals show significant differences based on the type of marriage?" are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

	Group	N	X	Ss	F	p
Marital Compatibility	Own choice	119	3,35	,66	,120	,887
	through arranged marriages	25	3,42	,63		
	through abduction	29	3,39	,75		

Marital Compatibility Levels by Marriage Type

(p<.05)

In Table 4, the results related to whether marital compatibility significantly differs based on the type of marriage show that marital compatibility does not significantly differ based on the type of marriage ($F = 0.120$; $p > 0.05$). In other words, there is no significant difference in the levels of marital compatibility based on the type of marriage.

The analysis results related to the fifth sub-goal of the study, which is the question "Do the marital compatibility levels of married individuals show significant differences based on their employment status?" are presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

Marital Compatibility Levels by Employment Status

Marital Compatibility		N	x	Ss	sd	t	p
Employment Status	yes	121	3,4	,74	,16	1,0	,312
	no	52	3,2	,49	,14		

(p<.05)

The test results in the table show that marital compatibility does not significantly differ based on employment status ($t = 1.0$; $p > 0.05$). In other words, there is no significant difference in the levels of marital compatibility based on employment status. However, when examining the mean scores of employed and unemployed married individuals, it was found that the mean score of employed individuals was higher than that of unemployed individuals, and this difference was statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Based on the first sub-goal of the study, the findings related to whether marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ according to the number of children revealed no significant difference between the number of children and marital compatibility. However, when examining the arithmetic mean values, it was found that couples without children and those with one child had higher levels of marital compatibility compared to the other groups. There could be several reasons why couples without children have higher marital compatibility scores. First, couples without children

may have more time and energy for their marriage. These couples may have more opportunities to strengthen their relationship and spend quality time together. Additionally, not having children can reduce financial and emotional stress for couples, which could positively impact marital compatibility. The care of a single child may be more manageable compared to the additional responsibilities and stress that come with having multiple children. This situation may allow couples to spend more time with each other and manage parenting-related stress more effectively.

Supporting this research, there are studies in the literature showing that couples without children have higher marital compatibility. In a study by Kubat [8], it was concluded that the number of children has no effect on marital happiness. Therefore, the findings of this research are consistent with those studies. On the other hand, in a study by, it was found that families with children had higher marital compatibility compared to families without children. While children may help keep the family together, they can also trigger conflicts between couples [9].

Based on the second sub-goal of the study, the findings related to whether marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ according to their monthly income showed that marital compatibility levels do not significantly differ based on the monthly income variable. However, when examining the arithmetic mean values based on participants income levels, it was observed that as income increased, marital compatibility also increased. It was found that the group with the highest level of marital compatibility also had the highest income level, while the group with the lowest marital compatibility had the lowest income level. Some studies in the literature have found that couples with lower economic conditions experience low economic status and job insecurity (especially for married men) are negatively related to marital compatibility [10]. Based on the third sub-goal of the study, the findings related to whether marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ according to the duration of marriage revealed no significant difference between marital compatibility and the duration of marriage. When examining the arithmetic mean values, it was found that couples who had been married for 1-5 years had higher levels of marital compatibility compared to the other groups. Similar to the findings of this study, Kubat [8] and Özmen Süataç [2] found in their research that as the duration of marriage increases, marital compatibility decreases, and that compatibility is higher in the early years of marriage.

Based on the fourth sub-goal of the study, the findings related to whether marital compatibility levels of married individuals differ according to their type of marriage showed that marital compatibility did not significantly differ based on the type of marriage. However, when examining the arithmetic mean values, it was found that those who married through arranged marriages had higher levels of marital compatibility compared to the other groups.

Arranged marriages typically involve the active participation of families and society. In such marriages, families may be involved in the process of evaluating whether the couple is compatible, and they can play a supportive role in the couple's married life. The support of families can help couples overcome challenges more easily and may enhance marital compatibility. Arranged marriages usually take place between people with similar social, cultural and economic status. Couples with similar values and beliefs may experience less conflict in their married life. Those who marry in this way may have fewer expectations from each other and the marriage may be based on more rational decisions, which may cause fewer problems in the relationship. On the other hand, couples who marry voluntarily or by running away often sign marriages where romantic feelings and individual preferences are at the forefront. Unrealistic expectations can lead to disappointment and relationship dissatisfaction. In such marriages, couples may come from different socio-cultural backgrounds, which can cause compatibility issues. However, couples who marry by choice or elopement often have a strong emotional bond, which can be considered an advantage of such marriages.

In a study conducted by Şendil and Korkut [11], it was found that marital compatibility was significantly higher among couples who married by mutual agreement compared to those who married through arranged marriages. In another study, it was found that individuals who married by their own choice had significantly higher marital compatibility than those who married through arranged marriages [12]. Based on the fifth sub-objective of the research, the findings regarding whether marital compatibility levels differ according to employment status revealed that there was no significant difference. However, when the mean scores of employed and non-employed married individuals were examined, it was found that employed individuals had higher mean scores for marital compatibility compared to non-employed individuals, and this difference was statistically significant.

According to the findings of Erdoğan's [13], study on the relationship between marital compatibility, psychological well-being, and loneliness, it was determined that the scores of participants who were actively employed in a job were significantly higher than those of non-employed participants, particularly in the overall marital compatibility score and the agreement sub-dimension. According to the results of Gergin's [14], study examining the marital compatibility of married women with employment and non-employment status, it was found that employed women had a higher level of marital happiness compared to non-employed women.

References

1. Özbek, C. (2018). Examination of the relationships between spouse evaluation, marital adjustment, marital satisfaction, and sexual satisfaction in married individuals. Master's Thesis. Near East University, Institute of Social Sciences, Clinical Psychology Department, Nicosia.
2. Özmen-Süataç, A. (2010). Investigation of marital adjustment in terms of interpersonal style and anger. Master's thesis, Ege University, İzmir.
3. Polat, D. (2006). Examination of the relationships between marital adjustment, tendencies toward infidelity, and conflict tendencies in married individuals in terms of some variables. Master's Thesis. Ankara University, Institute of Social Sciences, Psychology (Social Psyc) Department, Ankara.
4. Kublay, D., & Oktan, V. (2015). Marital adjustment: An investigation in terms of value preferences and subjective happiness. *Turkish Psychological Counseling and Guidance Journal*, 5(44), 25-35.
5. Erus, S. M. (2019). The mediating role of emotional intelligence and marital adjustment in the relationship between mindful awareness and subjective well-being in marriage. Doctoral Thesis. Yıldız Technical University, Institute of Social Sciences, Istanbul.
6. Çeliksoy, Ü. (2021). Examination of marriages in different age groups in terms of marital adjustment, family evaluation, and subjective well-being. Master's Thesis. Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Family Counseling Department, Family Counseling Science Department, Çanakkale.

7. Efiltili, E., Zhumgalbekov, A. (2024). Adaptation of the "Family Harmony" scale to the Kyrgyz language: Determining its validity and reliability. *Journal of Universities of Kyrgyzstan*, No. 3, 111-116. Эфилти Э., Жумгалбеков А.Ж. (2024). «Үй-бүлөлүк гармония» шкаласын кыргыз тилине адаптациялоо: валиддүүлүгүн жана ишенимдүүлүгүн аныктоо. *Известия ВУЗов Кыргызстана*,
8. Kubat, D. E. (2012). Examination of the relationship between tendencies toward infidelity and marital satisfaction in married individuals. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Haliç University, Institute of Social Sciences, Istanbul.
9. Bedir, İ. (2018). Investigation of variables predicting marital satisfaction in married individuals. Master's Thesis. Arel University, Institute of Social Sciences, Psychology Master's Program, Istanbul.
10. Pepping, C. A., & Halford, W. K. (2012). Attachment and relationship satisfaction in expectant first-time parents: The mediating role of relationship-enhancing behaviors. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 46(6), 770-774. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2012.08.005>.
11. Şendil, G., & Korkut, Y. (2008). Examination of couple adjustment and marital conflict in married couples from the perspective of demographic characteristics. *Psychology Studies*, 28, 15-34.
12. Arif, N., & Fatima, I. (2015). Marital satisfaction in different types of marriage. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 13(1), 36-40.
13. Erdoğan, T. (2022). The relationship between marital adjustment, psychological well-being, and loneliness. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Konya: Karatay University: Graduate Education Institute.
14. Gergin, K. (2023). Examination of marital adjustment in married working women and non-working married women. *Social, Humanities, and Administrative Sciences Journal*, 2023, 6(2), 183-204. DOI: 10.26677/TR1010.2023.1178 ISSN: 2667-422X Journal website: www.sobibder.org